

Scaling Under Dynamic Uncertainty Using Laws of Growth

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Abstract

This paper gives an overview of methods used to describe uncertainty in size range development. Laws of growth, scenario laws of growth and probabilistic laws of growth are extended to allow the calculation of dynamic, size-dependent product behaviour. Dynamic product behaviour can depend on time or load cycles, such as corrosion and wear. Effects such as these can be size-dependent, an issue that is also considered in this paper. The extended methods are explained using a pushrod as an example product.

1. Introduction

When designing size ranges, a product developer faces a special challenge: in addition to the occurrence of uncertainty during the design process, production processes and the usage of the product are often size-dependent. This can be demonstrated with a pushrod as it is prone to buckling. Its critical load depends on production tolerances, which depend on the product's size [European standard EN IS 286-1:2010, 2010]. Its strength is also size-dependent if elastic-plastic buckling occurs. Size-dependency is also common for dynamic uncertainty. Dynamic uncertainty changes over time or a number of load cycles. In the pushrod, the influence of corrosion is time-dependent and constantly reduces the second moment of area, causing a reduction in the critical load and thus safety. If the rate of corrosion is constant and proportional to the exposed surface (ASTM, 2011), a large pushrod has its safety margin reduced at a slower rate than a small one. If there is degradation because of growing cracks (Schürmann, H., 2007), the dynamic uncertainty caused by stiffness reduction is also size-dependent but refers to the number of load cycles and the history of degradation rather than the time the product was in use.

Size-dependency refers to scaled product properties. That does not necessarily involve a change in geometric properties. Besides geometrical properties, force, power, temperature, stiffness, strength and various other mechanical, thermodynamic and optical properties can be scaled. An example that addresses these kinds of scaling is size ranges of combustion engines that can be found in the automotive industry. It is common to use one type of engine to cover a wide range of power needs. Changing the engine operating map, the amount of fuel burnt (and therefore the combustion temperature and mean pressure) and oxygen (provided by a turbocharger) are increased (Braess, Seifert, 2013), which leads to scaled loads, due to higher temperatures, and higher pressures during combustion.

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The literature contains various methods to describe wear, corrosion and aging ((Sommer, et al., 2014), (Grote K.-H., Antonsson E. K., 2008), (Elachachi et al., 2006), (Davis, 2000) and many more). However, the dynamic aspects of scale dependency are not taken into account (Lotz et al., 2014), or they are not directly applicable to size range development, e.g. Elachachi et al., 2006. The scale-dependency aspect of dynamic uncertainty is not part of the studies, e.g. Braghin, et al. (2006).

This paper proposes a general approach for handling dynamic, size-dependent uncertainty. The types of uncertainty that are addressed are stochastic (probabilistic) uncertainty and estimated uncertainty (Hanselka, Platz, 2010). Unknown uncertainty is not addressed in the following methods.

The aim is to describe product properties under uncertainty over the whole product lifecycle, including all its processes, and in correlation to its size. The size dependency is modelled using step factors and laws of growth as they are common in size range development (Feldhusen, Grote, 2013). Another possibility is to use dimensional analysis, which is not the focus of this paper.

2. Example Product

The example product is a buckling beam with either a full or hollow circular cross section since an ideal buckling beam, according to Euler, is simple enough to enable understanding of phenomenological problems of scaling and scaling tools can be applied. Since the approach of scaling under uncertainty introduced in Lotz et al (2014) is not time-dependent, the example product has to be amended to show time-dependent effects. Therefore, two case studies are used: one in which corrosion takes place so the product properties vary over time (this beam has a full cross section); and the other in which a buckling beam of hollow cross section has abrasion on its end planes.

In general, geometric similarity is maintained during the scaling process. This means that the inner diameter is 0.9 times the outer diameter of the hollow cross section beam for all sizes. The deviations created during production processes are growing, according to the law of growth of IT tolerance classes (European standard EN IS 286-1:2010, 2010). Uncertainty occurring in measurement is not taken into account since the product properties are expressed as nominal values process in product development. The limit slenderness ratio is calculated using mechanical properties from Saarlstahl (2014), all sizes will reach elastic buckling before plastic deformation happens. All needed product properties are given in Tables 1, 2 and 3.

Table 1. General product properties of the buckling beam

Product property	Smallest step factor	Basic size	Largest step factor
<i>step factor</i>	0.2	1	5
<i>length l</i>	100 mm	500 mm	2,500 mm
<i>deviation Δl</i>	0.292 mm	0.5 mm	0.854 mm
<i>outer diameter $D=2r_o$</i>	2.4 mm	12 mm	60 mm
<i>deviation ΔD</i>	0.029 mm	0.05 mm	0.085 mm
<i>inner diameter $d=2r_i$</i>	2.16 mm	10.8 mm	54 mm
<i>deviation Δd</i>	0.029 mm	0.05 mm	0.085 mm
<i>Young's modulus</i>	E=210,000 N/mm ² ± 5,000 N/mm ²		
<i>Law of growth for geometrical deviations</i>	$\phi_{\Delta} = \phi_l^{1/3}$	$\phi_{\Delta} = \phi_l^{1/3}$	$\phi_{\Delta} = \phi_l^{1/3}$

These specifications can be used as input for laws of growth (LoG). Using laws of growth, all describing equations are written in step factors ϕ , which represents a nondimensional scaling factor for the size they represent, like $\phi_l = l_1/l_0$ which describes the scaling factor of a length (index 1) for a size range member (index 1) compared to the basic draft (index 0).

According to Euler (Grote/Antonsson, 2008), the critical load of the buckling beam (Figure 1a) with one end plane lying on a flat surface and having a simple support on the other is:

$$F_{krit} = \frac{EI(d_o, d_i)}{l^2} \quad (1)$$

Written with step factors defined previously, this leads to a law of growth for the critical load of the full section profiled beam (Equation 2 implies geometrical similarity).

$$\phi_{F_{krit}} = \phi_E \phi_l^2 \quad (2)$$

Two processes that affect product properties are used to examine time-dependent uncertainty: loss of material due to corrosion, which is size-independent; and abrasive wear, which is also size-dependent. Both are typical for uncertainty that occurs during usage of a product. All uncertainty measures in Tables 1, 2 and 3 are upper and lower bounds of intervals when calculating estimated uncertainty and, in the case of stochastic uncertainty, these values are considered to be six standard deviations away from the nominal (mean) value, following a Gaussian distribution.

Figure 1. a) The buckling beam under corrosion and its supports. b) Corrosive loads are taking effect on the outside of the beam with full cross section.

Figure 2. a) The buckling beam under abrasive loads and its supports. b) The cross section is hollow to achieve a nearly constant sliding speed over the whole cross section. c) The beam is rotating around its longitudinal axis.

2.1 Corrosive Loads

Regarding the corrosive loads, the buckling beam with full cross section (Figure 1b) is exposed to corrosion on its whole length. It is assumed that the corrosion rate will be constant along the beam. The length itself should be unaffected by corrosion. The corrosion rate that describes the material loss per time is according to (ASTM, 2011) and given by Equation 3:

$$C = (K \cdot W)/(A \cdot t \cdot \rho) \quad (3)$$

With K as a constant factor, depending on the case that is examined (material, environmental parameters...), W = weight loss in kg, A = area exposed to corrosion in m², t = time in s and

ρ = density in kg/m³. A common value for C, representing an ordinary low-carbon steel like 1.0402 (European standard EN 10027-2:, 1992) with 0.2% C in sulphuric acid (0.05%) at room temperature is taken from (Davis, 2000) (Table 2). Since the corrosion rate is very sensitive to concentration changes (at least at low concentrations like the one chosen) and is also influenced by the temperature, an estimated uncertainty of $\pm 20\%$ is applied.

A full cross section was chosen because the corrosion would have lowered the wall thickness of a tube, like the one used for wear load calculations, to a value where the failure mode changes from global buckling to local buckling of thin cylinders under axial compression. If the stability bounds of both failure modes are known, the following calculation methods can also handle these cases, but with increased complexity in mathematic modelling.

Table 2. Corrosion-related product properties, step factors as in Table 1.

Product property	Smallest step factor	Basic size	Largest step factor
C	0.4 mm/a	0.4 mm/a	0.4 mm/a
deviation ΔC	± 0.08 mm/a	± 0.08 mm/a	± 0.08 mm/a

2.2 Wear Loads

To have a size-dependent product property affecting process, wear loads are applied to the buckling beam. The buckling beam is made of 1.0503 steel at 206 HV 10 and turning unlubricated on its end plane, which is in contact with an even plate of the same material and hardness (Table 3, data from (Sommer, et al., 2014), and Figure 2). For easy formulation of the wear process, it has a hollow cross section with the wall thickness being small compared to the diameter. More complex wear processes can be calculated in the same way, but require sufficient mathematic modelling. The small wall thickness allows the assumption of a constant relative speed for the whole cross section while turning. The axial force F_{ab} causes the abrasion and should be proportional to the length of the beam $\varphi_{F_{ab}} = \varphi_l^{1,68}$. This proportionality results from the weight gain or loss of the geometrically similar upscaled or downscaled beam, the abrasive force is a result of the beam's own weight. Because the wear rate can be approximated in a linear relation to the axial force F_{ab} for a constant sliding speed of 0.07 m/s (Sommer, et al., 2014), size-dependent wear is the result (Table 3).

Table 3. Wear-related product properties, step factors as in Table 1.

Product property	Smallest step factor	Basic size	Largest step factor
constant Load F_{ab}	0.48 N $\pm$ 0.048 N	8.55 N $\pm$ 0.855 N	128.3 N $\pm$ 12.83 N
avg. pressure p	1.75 N/mm ²	1.25 N/mm ²	0.75 N/mm ²
avg. sliding speed v_s	0.07 m/s		
avg. wear rate w	10.5 mm/km	7.5 mm/km	4 mm/km

A linear approximation of the wear rate, depending on the pressure and valid for pressures between 0 N/mm² and 2 N/mm², can be calculated from the data given in Sommer, et al., 2014 as:

$$w = 6,3 \cdot p \quad (4)$$

To perform calculations that consider uncertainty, a deviation corresponding to Equation 4 is assigned to w , following the uncertainty of the diameters D and d as well as the uncertainty of the load F_{ab} and the uncertainty of the axial load. The sliding speed is considered to be exact.

3. Classification of Methods to handle Uncertainty in Size-Range Development

Several methods can support the designer with handling uncertainty in size-range development. Besides the use of dimensional analysis (nondimensional numbers and their deviation from the targeted mean value), which has been examined by the authors but is not included in this paper, there are several methods derived from laws of growth. Static scenario laws of growth (SLoG) and static probabilistic laws of growth (PLoG) have been published and evaluated (Lotz, et al., 2014). This paper tries to derive dynamic versions of these methods. Their relationship to each other can be found in Figure 3, where the information needed to perform calculations with those methods is plotted over their ability to handle dynamic uncertainty. The methods that need more information are also more computationally intensive, e.g. the Monte Carlo simulation for dynamic probabilistic laws of growth, and in some cases the dynamic scenario laws of growth. The approaches using dimensional analysis are especially suited to very low availability of information on mathematical modelling of the underlying physical effects, as long as measured data are available.

Figure 3. Different adaptations of scaling tools. Classification depending on the amount of information needed to perform their calculation and their ability to handle dynamic uncertainty.

3.1 Static laws of growth and static scenario laws of growth

Lotz et al. (2014) propose to assemble additional laws of growth, called scenario laws of growth. The most common are the best and worst case SLoGs. Therefore, the law of growth of geometrical deviations can be integrated into the law of growth for the critical load, and deviations of product properties, like Young's modulus, are written as minimum or maximum step factors. The minimum step factor that describes the worst case scenario is given by Equation 5; the maximum step factor, describing the best case scenario, can be assembled the same way, inverting addition and subtraction in the brackets (Lotz et al., 2014).

$$\phi_{F_{crit,min}} = \frac{(l_0)^2 (r_1 - \Delta r_0 \cdot \phi_l^{1/3})^4}{(r_0)^4 (l_1 + \Delta l_0 \cdot \phi_l^{1/3})^2} \cdot \phi_{E,min} \quad (5)$$

The SLoG growth especially helps in handling static estimated uncertainty. Estimated uncertainty (Hanselka, Platz, 2010) occurs, for example, if an interval in which the possible values for a product property are contained, but it is uncertain how they are distributed within the interval.

3.2 Dynamic Laws of Growth

Dynamical product behaviour is well represented by the methods of size range development. There are various similar relations that describe dynamic system behaviour, for example Newton's, Cauchy's, Froude's or Reynold's numbers. However, the calculations performed with them are still static ones and do not take into account that input product properties change during processes such as aging, corrosion and wear. In order to have a distinguished understanding of dynamic laws of growth, the following definition is proposed: "A *dynamic law of growth describes size-dependent product properties that are changed by time or load cycle-dependent processes.*" A core element is that dynamic laws of growth are still meant to support size range development so they should use step factors as variables. An initial approach to describe time (t) or load cycle (N) dependent laws of growth is to make the step factors time or load cycle-dependent:

$$\phi_i = f(t) \quad \text{or} \quad \phi_i = f(n) \quad (6)$$

They work in the same way and sometimes (if time and load cycles are coupled by the load cycle's frequency) can be converted into the other type.

Implementing a time dependency in step factors, the step factors are no longer nominal values as commonly used in size range development. They change with the time variable. The idea behind this is to have a justified tool to describe size and time-dependent product properties, like the scenario laws of growth do just for size dependency. The critical load is such a product property in the context of the introduced example product.

First, it is necessary to determine which of the step factors time dependency is influenced by. These step factors have to be adjusted to the dynamic behaviour of the product property. For the buckling bar under corrosion, as specified in Section 2, only the beam's diameter is affected. This means that there is no geometric similarity during the time of usage of this product. The loss of geometric similarity also happens when the geometric properties are affected in a different way to each other. Therefore, dynamic laws of growth usually will include more step factors than static ones. The time dependency is as shown in Equation 7 (compare with Equations 1 and 2):

$$\phi_{F_{crit}}(t) = \frac{\phi_E \cdot \phi_d(t)^4}{\phi_l^2} \quad (7)$$

Taking into account Equation 6 for $\phi_d(t)$, this becomes

$$\phi_d(t) = \frac{d_1 - c \cdot t}{d_0} \quad (8)$$

This would cause the dynamic law of growth (DLOG) to consist of terms that have no step factors in common, which prevents the scaling problem from being solved using only step factors as an expression of a scaling factor. To avoid this, Equation 8 can be split into two step factors: one which represents the factor of geometric scaling of the diameter, and the other which represents the dynamic behaviour. In this case, the second step factor is equal to the loss of material due to corrosion. In general, it can be called the step factor of time $\phi_{t,i}$ with an index i for the parameter it has influence on.

$$\phi_d(t) = \frac{d_1 - c \cdot t}{d_0} = \frac{d_1}{d_0} - \frac{c \cdot t}{d_0} = \phi_d - \phi_{t,d} \quad (9)$$

The step factor of time only depends on time itself and factors being constant over the scaling process. It is a nondimensional number similar to that used in dimensional analysis (Gibbings, 2011). Using the step factor of time, Equation 9 can be written as:

$$\phi_{F_{crit}}(t) = \frac{\phi_E \cdot (\phi_d - \phi_{t,d})^4}{\phi_l^2} \quad (10)$$

For the second example, the DLoG has a direct dependence on the number of revolutions N fulfilled by the beam (which is mathematically the same as a time dependency). This eases the calculation of product properties at a certain point of the product usage. If the wear rate w is written as step factor ϕ_w and ϕ_p is substituted through $\phi_{F_{ab}}/\phi_A$, $\phi_A = \phi_l^2$, the wear rate can be written as a size-dependent change in the product property:

$$\phi_w = \frac{\phi_l^{1,68}}{\phi_l^2} = \phi_l^{-0,32} \approx \frac{1}{\phi_l^{1/3}} \quad (11)$$

Since the uncertainty of the wear rate is not equal to the uncertainty of the length it should not be written as a function of ϕ_l within the DLoG. The quantification of uncertainty depends on which calculation is performed. For dynamic scenario laws of growth (DSL0G), the Uncertainty of ϕ_w follows the defined scenarios, in this case a combination of values that create a best or worst case. For probabilistic calculations, the probability density functions for the underlying parameters have to be convolved for a quantification of ϕ_w 's uncertainty. The DLoG for the beam under abrasive loads above is the following (if geometrical similarity is retained):

$$\phi_{F_{crit}} = \frac{\phi_E \cdot \phi_l^4}{\phi_l^2 \left(\frac{1-\pi \cdot N_1 \cdot w_1}{1-\pi \cdot N_0 \cdot w_0} \right)^2} = \frac{\phi_E \cdot \phi_l^2}{\phi_l^2 \cdot \phi_w^2} \quad \text{with} \quad \phi_w = \left(\frac{1-\pi \cdot N_1 \cdot w_1}{1-\pi \cdot N_0 \cdot w_0} \right)^2 \quad (12)$$

If geometric similarity is not retained the dynamic law of growth gets very complicated and it should be considered as approximating the bulky terms with terms that depend on less parameters or are in a monomial form, depending from the main parameter (ϕ_l for the example product) that can be transformed into a law of growth easily.

3.3 Dynamic Scenario Laws of Growth

Referring to Paragraph 3.1, laws of growth can be supplemented by scenarios deriving best or worst case scenarios (or other specific ones, if needed). This approach can also be applied to dynamic scenario laws of growth. Equation 10 can be adjusted to scenarios, usually best and worst case. For corrosion loads like those in the example products, the parameters that have uncertainty are the geometric parameters, as well as Young's modulus and the corrosion rate. The time can be considered accurate if it is not one of the dependent product properties (a cycle time, for example). Best and worst case scenarios are given in Equation 5. Equation 13 gives the result of combining Equations 10 and 5:

$$\phi_{F_{crit,min}}(t) = \frac{\phi_{E,min} \cdot (\phi_{d,min} - \phi_{t,d,max})^4}{\phi_{l,max}^2} \quad \text{and} \quad \phi_{F_{crit,max}}(t) = \frac{\phi_{E,max} \cdot (\phi_{d,max} - \phi_{t,d,min})^4}{\phi_{l,min}^2} \quad (13)$$

Scenarios of the step factor of time depend on the uncertainty of the corrosion rate. The boundaries of the intervals containing the product properties are identical to the tolerances given in Tables 1, 2 and 3. A representation of the dynamic scenario laws of growth is shown in Figure 4. Large deviations from the nominal product properties occur the longer the beam was exposed to the corrosive medium. Decreasing size of the product itself leads to larger deviations in product properties (the non-varying corrosion rate is larger compared to the diameter the smaller the diameter gets, in addition the relative tolerances are larger (Table 1)).

Figure 4. Dynamic Scenario Laws of Growth for the buckling beam under corrosion.

A schematic overview of the steps needed to calculate a DStoG is presented in Figure 5.

3.4. Probabilistic Laws of Growth and Dynamic Probabilistic Laws of Growth

Probabilistic laws of growth (PLog) are introduced by Lotz et al. (2014) and are an approach to handling size-dependent uncertainty. The main focus lies on stochastic uncertainty in the definition of Hanselka & Platz (2010). Using Monte Carlo simulation, the probability density functions (PDF) of the target parameter of scaling can be calculated from the PDF of the input parameters. Therefore, the static laws of growth for product properties and uncertainty have to be known. If the PDF of the input parameters are all uniform or all Gaussian in type, the calculations can also be performed analytically instead of numerically (Joint Committee for Guides in Metrology, 2008). In addition to Lotz et al. (2014), laws of growth can be approximated for statistical parameters such as standard deviation, skewness and kurtosis of the target parameter PDF. Procedures to derive laws of growth from data are introduced by Pahl & Rieg (1984), Most (1989) and Kloberdanz (1991). The data in this case are standard deviations or other statistical parameters calculated for several sizes of the type range.

The approach for how to derive DPLogS is shown in Figure 5. The mathematical model of physical relationships between the input parameters is assembled and a static law of growth is derived. As in DLogS, the initial values (for $t=0$ or $N=0$) for the dynamic calculation of time-dependent product properties are obtained by performing the targeted product properties of the product's size range. This generates SLogS or PLogS, depending on what information about uncertainty is available. In a second step, the law of growth for the time dependency of product properties is derived: the DLog. In the third step, the initial values are processed using the DLog; this can be done in an analytic manner for SLogS (Paragraph 3.3) or via Monte Carlo simulation for PLogS, especially if the PDFs of the uncertainty are asymmetric.

Having carried this out using Monte Carlo simulation for the beam under corrosive loads, histograms can be plotted, which would be nondescriptive for the example product with only Gaussian PDFs as input, or the plot of a confidence belt (6σ or 99.99966% in this case) can be assembled (Figure 6). The beam under abrasive load shows similar behaviour, except the critical load grows because of the decreasing length of the beam. Due to limited space, plots cannot be given here but can be requested from the authors.

Figure 5. Approach for handling dynamic probabilistic uncertainty in size range development.

Figure 6. Comparison between the DSLoG and DPLoG for the beam under corrosive loads at different sizes. The legend is valid for both plots.

4. Comparison

The dynamic scenario laws of growth are consistent with the underlying physical laws and can be considered as a reliable source of absolute best and worst-case output values, especially for dynamic laws of growth. This is just the opposite to the behaviour that static laws of growth show, since they are not necessarily showing the absolute best or absolute worst case if compared to the PDFs calculated with Monte Carlo simulation for a targeted level of safety (Lotz, et al., 2014). The reason for this deviation in reliability of the outcomes lies in the way the probabilistic dynamic law of growth is calculated and its boundary conditions. If the Input parameters are changing with a high frequency compared to the time the product is exposed to this uncertainty, the product behaviour will only have minor deviations from the mean value. This is reasonable in terms of the law of large numbers: the more frequent the stochastic value changes, the better the mean value describes the product's behaviour (the mean value

is identical to the nominal value for all symmetrical PDFs, like the Gaussian or uniform distribution). The important aspect is that uncertainty with adequate change frequency (in this case, 1,000 changes over five years or 1,000,000 load cycles were more than enough) and common strengths of effect on the product property lead to a product behaviour that can be predicted very well with DSLoGs. If a very precise prediction is needed, DPLoGs are a helpful way to reduce excessive margins of safety. Nevertheless, there is one exceptional case. If the further change in product properties depends on the history of change in this property, the standard deviation will be larger. A technical example is the degradation of fibre-reinforced plastics. If there are high loads in the first load cycles, and degradation starts because inter-fibre fracture occurs, the strength is decreased and smaller loads would cause progression of the degradation where they would not have degraded the material if it had not been damaged before (Schürmann, 2007). These processes can also be handled with probabilistic laws of growth, although the mathematical modelling is more complex since differential equations have to be solved. There are often more interdependencies between the different step factors. The calculation can only be performed by integration or use of numerical methods.

5. Outlook

The insights gained working with DSLoGs and DPLoGs create areas of interest for future research. A catalogue of time-dependent step factor modelling for scenarios of wear, abrasion, aging, etc should be assembled to ease the product developer's task of deriving dynamic laws of growth. Strategies for efficiently handling the computationally intensive calculation of DPLoGs should be integrated into detailed programming instructions. In addition, development of product and process models that focus on scaling effects could support the product developer in identifying the critical parameters that have to be examined in a detailed way, e.g. with DPLoGs, and those that can be handled with less costly methods, such as DSLoGs or even DLoGs. The models could also help find the limits to scaling of a product, which is an important issue when planning a size range.

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